

Studies on Sulphonamides. Part V. Preparation, Antibacterial and Antifungal Activity of 4 : 4'-Bis arylsulphonamidostilbene 2 : 2'-disulphonic Acids

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Substituted benzenesulphonamides were prepared from 4 : 4'-diaminostilbene 2 : 2'-disulphonic acid and tested for antibacterial as well as antifungal activity *in vitro*. Halogen substituted sulphonamides were found to be active against *S. Aureus*, *E. coli* and *A. niger*.

SULPHONAMIDES have been reported to be pharmacodynamic versatile compounds for the diseases like cancer¹, tuberculosis², diabetes³, malaria⁴, leprosy⁵ and convulsant⁶. Substituted stilbene derivatives have been found to possess antiviral activity⁷. Northey⁸ and co-workers reported that 4, 4'-Di-*p*-aminobenzene sulphonamidostilbene-2, 2'-disulphonic acid was found to be inactive. We have prepared 4 : 4'-Bis arylsulphonamidostilbene 2, 2'-disulphonic acids of the type (A) (where R is equal to phenyl, *p*-tolyl, *p*-anisyl, *p*-chlorophenyl, *p*-bromophenyl, *p*-iodophenyl, *p*-acetamidophenyl α - and β -naphthyl) by condensing 4 : 4'-diaminostilbene 2 : 2'-disulphonic acid with different arylsulphonyl chlorides. The products obtained were purified and tested for antibacterial as well as antifungal activity using cup-plate method.

to the solution of arylsulphonyl chloride (0.01 mole) in acetone (10 ml.) and refluxed in water bath at 80-85° for half an hour. The contents were poured into crushed ice and solution obtained was acidified by dilute hydrochloric acid (congo red). The product obtained was filtered, washed with cold water, dried and crystallised from ethanol. Physical constants of these compounds are recorded in table.

(a) Antibacterial Activity :

The nutrient agar prepared by the usual method was inoculated aseptically with 0.5 ml. of 24 hrs. old subculture of *S. aureus* and *E. coli* in separate conical flasks at 40-45° and mixed well by gentle shaking. About 25 ml. of the contents of a flask were evenly spread in a petridish (13 cm. in diameter) and

(A)

Experimental

Preparation of 4 : 4'-Bis arylsulphonamidostilbene 2 : 2'-disulphonic acids :

4 : 4'-Diaminostilbene 2 : 2'-disulphonic acid (0.005 mole) dissolved in pyridine (5 ml) was added

allowed to settle for 2 hrs. The cups (10 m.m. in diameter) were punched in a petridish and loaded with 0.1 ml. (10 mg/ml) of solution of a sample in DMF by means of a sterile 1 ml. pipette. The plates were incubated at 37° for 24 hrs. and zone of inhibition as a diameter of each spot was measured in mm. after 24 hrs. The difference of diameter of the zone

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Table—Physical data and antimicrobial screening of sulphonamides of the type (A).

Sr. No.	R	Molecular Formula	% yield	m. p. °C	% Found	Nitrogen Cal.	Zone of inhibition in m.m.		
							<i>S. aureus</i> (24 hrs.)	<i>E. coli</i> (24 hrs.)	<i>A. niger</i> (72 hrs.)
1.	C ₆ H ₅	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₁₀ N ₄ S ₄	62.58	215d.	4.29	4.31	25	22	20
2.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ O ₁₀ N ₄ S ₄	74.80	232-35d	4.10	4.13	28	25	26
3.	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ O ₁₂ N ₄ S ₄	67.43	225-30d	4.00	3.94	25	20	18
4.	<i>p</i> -Cl-C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ O ₁₀ N ₄ S ₄ Cl ₂	59.42	272d	3.87	3.90	31	29	29
5.	<i>p</i> -Br-C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ O ₁₀ N ₄ S ₄ Br ₂	65.38	265d	3.45	3.47	28	20	26
6.	<i>p</i> -I-C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ O ₁₀ N ₄ S ₄ I ₂	62.84	2.40-43d	3.08	3.1	30	30	25
7.	<i>p</i> -NHCOCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	C ₃₀ H ₂₆ O ₁₂ N ₄ S ₄	72.30	250-55d	7.30	7.33	28	25	25
8.	α -C ₁₀ H ₇	C ₃₄ H ₂₆ O ₁₀ N ₄ S ₄	60.39	220-23d	3.70	3.73	25	16	29
9.	β -C ₁₀ H ₇	C ₃₄ H ₂₆ O ₁₀ N ₄ S ₄	55.85	173-75	3.77	3.73	24	22	20

of inhibition of the test solution and that of the control gives the actual diameter of the zone of inhibition of the test compound (recorded in table). Phenol solution 5% was used as reference antibacterial and solvent DMF was also put to know if it showed any activity against these organisms.

From the experimental data it was observed that halogen substituted sulphonamides possess high activity as compared to other substituents like phenyl, *p*-tolyl, *p*-anisyl etc. against *S. aureus* and *E. coli*.

(b) Antifungal Activity :

The above mentioned sulphonamide derivatives were tested for fungicidal activity by cup-plate method using *Aspergillus niger* and sabourauds agar medium. All the plates were incubated at room temperature and results were recorded after 72 hrs.

From the experimental data it was observed that *p*-tolyl, *p*-chlorophenyl and α -naphthylsulphonamides were highly active against *Aspergillus niger*.

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